

Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maxima of Nitrobenzaldehydes by some Uni- and Poly-valent Cations and Anions *vis-a-vis* the Kinetics of Electrode Reaction

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The suppression of the polarographic negative maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes (*ortho* isomer does not yield a maximum) in borax-boric acid buffer of pH 7.1 has been attempted at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using some uni- and poly-valent cations and anions, *vis.* Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Al^{3+} ; and CNS^- , I^- , oxalate and citrate as suppressors. The electrode reactions of the depolarisers have been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible in the presence of different amounts of these suppressors. The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,n}^0$) have been calculated by Koutecky's method.

ACCORDING to Meites¹, in the presence of surfactants, the structure of the double layer at the solution-mercury (dme) interface is greatly influenced. This implies that the study of the electrode kinetics of a depolariser is greatly influenced if its reduction at the dme is studied in the presence of conventional surfactants used as maxima suppressors. It is in this background that the suppression of polarographic maxima of nitrobenzaldehydes has been contemplated by uni- and poly-valent cations and anions with a view to studying their electrode kinetics. Hence the title study has been undertaken.

Experimental

The experimental details were the same as reported earlier². The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes was determined by the millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon³ and was found to be 8 for *ortho* and *para* isomers, and 6 for the *meta* isomer. The diffusion coefficient (D) of each depolariser was obtained from the Ilkovic equation. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,n}^0$) were calculated from the plots of $\log k_{f,n}^0$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements the current at the end of the drop (*i.e.* maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites⁴. The following uni- and poly-valent cations and anions were used: cations (nitrate being the anion in each case): Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Al^{3+} ; anions (potassium being the cation in each case): CN_3^- , I^- , oxalate and citrate. The dme had the following capillary characteristics (in 0.1M NaNO_3 , in open circuit): $m=3.16 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=2.46 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.5 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$, $h_{\text{corr}}=36.2 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

In BR-buffer of pH 7.1, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes (in 4%, v/v, ethanolic solution) yield sharp and well defined maxima which lie at -0.66 and -0.56 V (*vs* sce), respectively from the potential of electro-capillary zero, which is -0.32 V (*vs* sce) under the same experimental conditions. Since $E_{1/2}$ values of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes at pH 7.1 lie on negative side of the electro-capillary zero, the maxima of these depolarizers are of negative polarity⁵. The relative heights of these maxima are in the following order: *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde > *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde.

The effect of increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions on the maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes has been studied. Typical values of E_{max} and i_{max} have been presented in Table I for Na^+ and I^- ions only; the results for other cations and anions mentioned are similar. A perusal of Table I shows that with the addition of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions, the value of i_{max} decreases and that of E_{max} gets shifted to positive potentials. Singh *et al.*⁶ have put forward an explanation for this positive shift in E_{max} . After the suppression of the maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes by the requisite amounts of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions, *o*- and *m*-nitrobenzaldehydes yield, in each case, a well defined two-step reduction wave while the *para* isomer yields a well defined three-step reduction wave at pH 7.1. The wave-heights of all the steps are diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the linearity of i_d vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin. Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes in the presence of increasing concentrations of uni- and

TABLE 1—VALUES OF POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (α_{n_a} AND $k_{f,h}^0$) FOR IRREVERSIBLE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF *o*-, *m*- AND *p*-NITROBENZALDEHYDES (IN 4% ETHANOLIC SOLUTIONS) IN PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF UNI- AND POLY-VALENT CATIONS AND ANIONS AT pH 7.1

[Ion] <i>M</i>	$-E_{max}$ (vce) V	$-E_{1/2}$ (vce) V	i_{max} μA	i_d μA	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ $cm^2 s^{-1}$	α_{n_a}	$K_{f,h}^0$ $cm s^{-1}$
<i>o</i>-Nitrobenzaldehyde								
0.0 I	—	0.375	—	20.40	62	8.91	0.82	1.52×10^{-5}
II	—	1.315	—	21.76	115		0.42	1.98×10^{-11}
Cation								
Na⁺								
4.00 I	—	0.395	—	18.70	65	7.40	0.83	2.01×10^{-5}
II	—	1.325	—	19.72	125		0.49	2.76×10^{-11}
4.50 I	—	0.390	—	17.00	65	6.27	0.85	4.86×10^{-5}
II	—	1.305	—	18.86	123		0.44	4.02×10^{-11}
5.00 I	—	0.392	—	16.32	66	5.45	0.86	8.30×10^{-5}
II	—	1.300	—	16.66	121		0.44	4.17×10^{-11}
Anion								
I⁻								
0.125	—	0.390	—	18.70	65	7.01	0.83	5.17×10^{-5}
0.250	—	0.386	—	19.72	63		7.80	0.85
0.500	—	0.380	—	20.40	62	8.34	0.86	8.06×10^{-5}
<i>m</i>-Nitrobenzaldehyde								
0.00	0.66	—	38.76	—	—	—	—	—
Cation								
Na⁺								
0.50	0.65	—	36.04	—	—	—	—	—
1.00	0.62	—	32.64	—	—	—	—	—
2.50	0.57	—	23.12	—	—	—	—	—
4.00	0.56	—	19.36	—	—	—	—	—
4.50* I	—	0.370	—	18.70	58	8.53	0.93	6.39×10^{-7}
II	—	1.180	—	12.24	75		0.72	1.62×10^{-15}
5.00 I	—	0.365	—	18.02	57	7.98	0.94	7.92×10^{-7}
II	—	1.160	—	11.90	74		0.73	3.16×10^{-15}
5.50 I	—	0.350	—	17.68	56	7.27	0.95	8.96×10^{-7}
II	—	1.120	—	10.88	72		0.75	8.30×10^{-15}
Anion								
I⁻								
1.00	0.62	—	32.64	—	—	—	—	—
2.00	0.60	—	28.22	—	—	—	—	—
3.50	0.58	—	24.82	—	—	—	—	—
4.20	0.58	—	21.42	—	—	—	—	—
4.25* I	—	0.440	—	21.08	57	9.10	0.94	5.17×10^{-7}
II	—	1.280	—	10.82	73		0.74	2.11×10^{-15}
4.50 I	—	0.432	—	18.02	56	6.59	0.95	6.32×10^{-7}
II	—	1.260	—	9.18	70		0.77	3.61×10^{-15}
4.75 I	—	0.415	—	17.68	56	6.11	0.96	8.71×10^{-7}
II	—	1.250	—	8.50	69		0.78	4.02×10^{-15}
<i>p</i>-Nitrobenzaldehyde								
0.0	0.56	—	30.94	—	—	—	—	—
Cation								
Na⁺								
2.0×10^{-3}	0.53	—	27.54	—	—	—	—	—
3.0×10^{-3}	0.49	—	23.80	—	—	—	—	—
2.0×10^{-2}	0.45	—	19.72	—	—	—	—	—
2.4×10^{-2}	0.44	—	18.02	—	—	—	—	—
2.8×10^{-2} I	—	0.370	—	17.68	67	6.15	0.81	2.49×10^{-5}
II	—	1.240	—	9.52	87		0.62	4.75×10^{-14}
III	—	1.380	—	7.82	68		0.81	8.75×10^{-10}
1.00 I	—	0.335	—	17.84	66	4.80	0.83	3.41×10^{-5}
II	—	1.205	—	7.82	85		0.68	6.21×10^{-14}
III	—	1.335	—	5.78	67		0.80	9.11×10^{-10}
2.00 I	—	0.320	—	17.00	65	5.49	0.83	8.78×10^{-5}
II	—	1.195	—	7.82	83		0.65	2.82×10^{-15}

(Table 1 contd.)

Anion								
I ⁻								
4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.51	—	28.56	—	—	—	—	—
8.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.50	—	22.10	—	—	—	—	—
2.50	0.48	—	20.74	—	—	—	—	—
3.00	0.48	—	19.98	—	—	—	—	—
3.10*	I	0.382	—	19.04	67	—	0.81	6.02 × 10 ⁻⁵
	II	1.245	—	9.18	83	7.66	0.65	5.16 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
	III	1.980	—	10.88	68	—	0.80	4.12 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
3.50	I	0.375	—	17.68	66	—	0.82	8.18 × 10 ⁻⁵
	II	1.230	—	8.84	82	6.51	0.66	6.29 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
	III	1.970	—	9.52	67	—	0.82	6.68 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
3.75	I	0.370	—	17.00	64	—	0.86	9.32 × 10 ⁻⁵
	II	1.220	—	7.82	80	5.68	0.67	8.68 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
	III	1.960	—	8.84	65	—	0.83	8.96 × 10 ⁻¹⁰

I=First wave, II=second wave and III=third wave.

* Concentration at which the maximum gets just suppressed.

poly-valent cations and anions were applied. The slope values of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical values expected for 8- and 6-electron reversible reduction processes. It follows from this that the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes is irreversible⁷. The dependence of current on h_{corr} at different stages of the wave was also studied and the current was found to be independent of the pressure head of the mercury at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave, thereby supporting the irreversible nature of the polarographic reduction^{8,9}.

The values of αn_a and $k_{t,h}^0$ for the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes tend to increase with increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions. This shows¹⁰ that the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes at dme is rendered less irreversible with increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions.

A comparison of $k_{t,h}^0$ values at the stage where maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes get just suppressed by uni- and poly-valent cations and anions (*ortho* isomer does not give maximum) may give a quantitative estimation of the influence of these ions on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes. From a perusal of Table 1 the following order of $k_{t,h}^0$ values in respect of various uni- and poly-valent cations and anions is obtained. Uni- and poly-valent cations: $Al^{3+} > Ca^{2+} > Na^+$. Thus, among the uni- and poly-valent cations it is Al^{3+} which suppresses the maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reactions. Uni- and poly-valent anions: $CNS^- > I^- > (citrate)^{3-} > (oxalate)^{2-}$. Thus, among the uni- and poly-valent anions it is CNS^- which suppresses the maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reactions.

The order of $k_{t,h}^0$ values in respect of the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes

in the presence of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions is as follows: *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde $>$ *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde $>$ *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde. Thus, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde is easiest to reduce at dme.

Relative efficacies of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions in the suppression of the maxima of m- and p-nitrobenzaldehydes on the basis of αn_a values: At the stage where the maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes just disappear (marked by an asterisk in Table 1), the order of αn_a values signifies⁶ the extent to which the addition of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions renders the electrode reactions of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes more irreversible from the position in the absence of these ions. In other words, a cation or an anion for which αn_a has got a higher value at the point of just suppression of the maxima will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes. On this basis, the following order of relative efficacies of various uni- and poly-valent cations and anions has been established. Uni- and poly-valent cations: $Al^{3+} > Ca^{2+} > Na^+$. Uni- and poly-valent anions: $CNS^- > I^- > (citrate)^{3-} > (oxalate)^{2-}$.

It is interesting to note that not only uni- and poly-valent cations but also anions suppress the negative maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes and that their (cations and anions) efficacies follow the valency rule. However, I^- and CNS^- do not follow this generalisation. This may be attributed to the fact that both I^- and CNS^- are capillary active substances¹¹ and as such they are more effective in suppressing the maxima. Further, the order of efficacies found on the basis of molarity is identical to that obtained on the basis of αn_a values.

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